

14-16
NOV
2018

OPEN SCIENCE FORUM

#LUXOSE

seminars
debates
workshops

to make your

visible
RESEARCH
transparent
efficient

Luxembourg Learning Centre,
Campus Belval, Luxembourg

openscience2018.uni.lu

